

Research

The impact of Nano-ZnO micronutrient fertilizer on growth and yield parameters of commercially-cultivated traditional rice varieties (*Oryza sativa* L.) in Sri Lanka

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Abstract: Inbred rice varieties are popular among Sri Lankan paddy farmers owing to their high performance related to yield, nutrition, biotic and abiotic resistance. Though traditional rice varieties offer high nutritional value and medicinal properties than the inbred versions, their characteristic low yield tends to discourage paddy farmers. This choice of one variety over the other is also affected by cereal-grown soils which show micronutrient deficiency such as Zn and Cu, which adversely affects the growth and yield performance of rice. The present research was carried out to determine the effects of nano-ZnO micronutrient fertilizer on the growth and yield of four (04) selected commercially-cultivated traditional rice varieties, *Kalu Heenati*, *Kuruluthuda*, *Pachchap-erumal* and *Suwandel*. Two commercially-cultivated inbred varieties, Bg360 and Bg94-1 were used as a reference. Nano-ZnO fertilizer was synthesized by Sol-gel method and was used in spray applications at a concentration of 30, 60 and 120 mg L⁻¹ (F1, F2 and F3) and double deionized water served as the control (F0). Treatments were carried out at two stages: during the bearing stage [at 48-58 Days after sowing (DAS)] and the grain filling stage [(100-105 DAS)].

A Complete Randomized Block Design was employed with three blocks and five replicates in each block. Growth parameters, plant height and Chlorophyll content were recorded during 30, 60 and 90DAS. The yield characters were measured at harvest. Data were subjected to univariate analysis of variance (3-way ANOVA) to assess the interaction between the rice varieties, fertilizer treatment and DAS. Percentage grain filling and 100 grains-weight were significantly increased ($p \leq 0.05$) with the foliar application of nano-ZnO fertilizer. Foliar application of nano-ZnO-fertilizer has a considerable effect on yield/reproductive parameters, but, there was no significant effect on growth parameters in traditional rice varieties with nano-ZnO fertilizer. Yield increment in the selected traditional rice varieties was prominent compared to the two inbred varieties used as references.

There is a potential to expand commercial cultivation of traditional rice varieties through foliar application of nano fertilizers. However, in-depth studies are required to optimize the nano-ZnO fertilizer concentration and the time of application to obtain the maximum productivity in traditional rice varieties cultivated in Sri Lanka.

Keywords: Traditional rice, Nano-fertilizer, Nano-ZnO, *Oryza sativa* L.

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Introduction

Global crop production heavily depends on fertilizer input to increase the growth potential of agricultural lands. Yet, the engagement between the natural land and fertilizers has always been a problematic act giving credence to many ideas and arguments about environment pollution—including permanent damage to the soil—and life-diminishing diseases. In the 1960s, the world underwent a research-governed crop production practice called *The Green Revolution* (or *The Third Agricultural Revolution*), an initiative launched primarily by developing countries to significantly increase crop production through extensive use of artificial fertilizers, pesticides as well as high-yielding crop varieties. However, subsequent research argued that this practice caused extensive damage to soil by causing widespread nutrient deficiency in agricultural lands around the world which significantly decreased crop yield. For example, there was a reported decrease in the micronutrients, the natural elements essential for plant growth in agricultural lands in many parts of the world (Duhana *et al.*, 2017). In recent years, it has been reported that around 50% of the cereal-growing land was deficient in Zinc and 30% of the cultivated soil has suffered from decreased amounts of Iron. The worldwide crop production, researchers claimed, is thus seriously affected by micronutrient deficiency in soil (Das, 2014). Though chemical fertilizers could be considered the immediate response to this situation, large-scale usage of chemical fertilizers, researchers argue, is not a sustainable solution in the long run (Solanki *et al.*, 2015). Reportedly, during the last four decades, chemical fertilizer usage has increased in Asian countries (GRiSP, 2013). It was reported that after *The Green Revolution* era in India, nitrogen fertilizer usage in the form of urea has increased by 29%. Such high usage of nitrogen fertilizer is responsible for 80% of the atmospheric nitrous oxide, which eventually contribute to global warming (Duhana *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, the crop industry needs to re-think of strategies to use micro nutrients creatively and in an environment-friendly manner to create sustainable modes of crop production. The present study is such an attempt to locate and inform the crop industry of a South Asian country of a creative mode of growth based on the best use of fertilizer.

This study wishes to locate the impact of a specific micronutrient on a commercially-grown variety of rice in southern Sri Lanka with the motive of informing the crop industry of the best fertilizer practices. It will thus monitor the effect/s of foliar spray application of nano-ZnO micronutrient fertilizer on growth and yield of selected commercially-cultivated traditional rice varieties, *Kalu Heenati*, *Kuruluthuda*, *Pachchaperumal* and *Suwandel*. Rice is bonded to the lives of people in Asian countries, not only as a staple food but also as a cultural motif. For instance, in Sri Lanka, rice is a powerful motivator, thematic and a symbol bordering the sacred in folklore and folk culture, an in-depth discussion of which is beyond the scope of this study. Rice is a semi-aquatic annual plant of family Poaceae. The genus *Oryza* of family Poaceae comprise 22 species and out of these species, *Oryza sativa* and *Oryza glaberrima* are important for human consumption (Mutthayya *et al.*, 2014). About 8,000-15,000 years ago, *O. sativa* was first grown in Southeast Asia and about 3,000 years ago *O. glaberrima* was domesticated in Africa. There are three main ecological varieties of rice: 1) the long-grained *indica* variety that is mainly grown in tropical and subtropical Asia 2) the medium-grained *japonica* variety cultivated in the temperate regions of Asia and 3) the medium grained *javanica* rice grown in the South East Asia (Khush, 1997; Callaway, 2014)). Today, rice is the second largest commodity produced in the world and estimated to be the staple food of 3.5 billion people worldwide. The world had dedicated 162.3 million hectares for rice cultivation in all six continents except in Antarctica. Nearly 200 million households in the developing countries depend on the income generated by rice and rice farming has produced employment opportunities for 1.8million of people in Sri Lanka (DOA, 2022). The current global rice utilization is 480 million metric tons (MMT) per year and 85% of this amount is used for human consumption (Hiyasmin *et al.*, 2015; Chauhan *et al.*, 2017; Mutthayya *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, because of the remarkable ability of rice plants in tolerating diverse habitat conditions and the ability to be altered through crop improvement techniques to suit external conditions, rice has become the model monocot system for genetic and genomic studies (Shimamoto & Kyojuka, 2002). Thus, the present research adds an impetus to the industry of rice farming by focusing on the best nutrients that will improve crop output without causing soil damage.

According to International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) 2019, Zinc (Zn) is an important micronutrient in rice cultivation. Zinc is a crucial element for plant life as it plays a vital role in Chlorophyll production, maintains membrane activities, cytochrome and nucleotide synthesis, seed development and stalk maturation. When faced with severe Zn deficiency, tillering, or the formation of shoots from the base of the rice plant, is decreased and time taken for crop maturity is increased which eventually reduce the crop yield (Dobermann & Fairhurst, 2000). To remedy such conditions, application of Zn into the paddy fields is recommended by the Department of Agriculture, though many farmers disregard this recommendation. There are three ways to deliver agrochemicals into plants: seed treatments, soil amendment and foliar sprays (Mahil & Kumar, 2019). Although soil application is the most common method to supply essential nutrients to plants, higher plants can absorb mineral nutrients when applied as foliar sprays. It is reported that the foliar spray application of micronutrients would increase the uptake of the chemical elements through the leaves (Duhan *et al.*, 2017). Nano-fertilizers come handy in infusing those micronutrients into plants. It has been shown that the foliar application of nano-scale nutrients increases the nutrient uptake and the aerosol spray facilitates the even distribution of the nanoparticles (Mahil & Kumar, 2019).

Nanotechnology is one of the most important and innovative scientific tools in the world. The term nanotechnology which is abbreviated as nanotech is the manipulation of matter on an atomic and molecular scale (Qureshi *et al.*, 2018). At the nano scale the matter depicts altered properties which are acutely different from those observed at macroscopic level. Therefore, nanotechnology has a great potential to modify conventional agricultural practices and comes in handy in delivering fertilizers into the plants. Most of the conventional agrochemicals applied to the crops are lost and do not reach the target site due to several factors such as leaching, drifting, hydrolysis, photolysis, and microbial degradation. Nanoparticles and Nano capsules provide efficient means to distribute pesticides and fertilizers in a controlled fashion with high site specificity thus reducing collateral damage (Moore, 2006). In Sri Lanka, Nanotechnology is still at an emerging stage and its benefits are under-valued in the field of agriculture (Somaratne *et al.*, 2019).

Research Methodology

Selection and germination of traditional rice varieties

Traditional rice varieties *Kalu Heenati*, *Kuruluthuda*, *Pachchaperumal* and *Suwandel* were used in the study and the inbred varieties Bg360 and Bg94-1 which were developed at the Rice Research Development Institute (RRDI), Sri Lanka were used as references. *Kaluheenati* has a blackish lemma and pleat and produce red grains which is rich in iron and zinc. *Kuruluthuda* produces medium sized red grains enriched with protein, fiber and fatty acids. *Suwandel* is a white color small rice grain which has a distinct pleasant fragrance and contain carbohydrates, vitamins, fat and micronutrients. *Pachchaperumal* also known as *Siyapath el*, provides red color medium sized rice grains fortified with protein, vitamins, antioxidants and micronutrient. All these traditional varieties of rice have medicinal properties and are used frequently in traditional Ayurvedic remedies. Bg360 is commonly called *keeri samba* and Bg94-1 is a Nadu rice variety; and both have a reputation as high yielding inbred rice varieties. Rice varieties were selected based on: a) duration of cultivation b) suitability for lowland paddy cultivation (which require lots of water) c) nature of cultivated land, whether grown in flooded or irrigated lands) popularity among Sri Lankan farmers, consumers and rice distributors. Seed materials were collected from RRDI.

The seeds were germinated in a growth chamber with one-week old seedlings transplanted in pots. Five seedlings were planted in each pot (diameter 25.00cm, height 22.00 cm). Pots were filled with a soil mixture (potting mixture and paddy soil in 1:1 ratio). N, P, K fertilizer were added to the pots according to the recommendation of Department of Agriculture, Sri Lanka before transplanting the seedlings. The pot-level experiment was carried out in the polyvinyl house. The factorial experiment (rice variety and treatment) was employed in the experiment based on Completely Randomized Block Design (CRBD) with twenty replicates.

Nano-ZnO preparation and characterization

Nano-ZnO was prepared via Sol-gel method in the study (Saravanan *et al.*, 2012; Saravanan *et al.*, 2011). The precursor chemicals Zinc acetate [$\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$], NaOH and isopropyl alcohol (2-propanol) with high purity (> 99.5 %) were used in this study to prepare nano fertilizers. All the chemicals and reagents used in this study are of analytical grade. All aqueous solutions were prepared using deionized double distilled water.

Nanoparticles were characterized with XRD (X-Ray diffraction), SEM/TEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy/Transmission Electron Microscopy) to confirm their physical properties, viz. structure, morphology, and elemental composition.

Prepared Nano-ZnO particles were characterized with Bruker D8 Focus X-ray diffractometer. Samples were compressed onto the sample holder and the X-ray diffraction patterns were recorded under the following conditions: Cu-K α radiation (1.54Å), a voltage of 40kV, a current of 40mA, 2θ range from 10° to 20° and a scan speed of 1sec/step. Average crystallite size of the nanoparticles was calculated using the Scherrer equation.

$$D = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where, k = Scherrer's constant, λ = wavelength of X-rays, θ = Bragg's diffraction angle, β = full width at half maximum and D = crystallite size (Scherrer, 1918; Langford & Wilson, 1978).

To confirm the physical properties, viz. structure, and surface morphology of the synthesized nano particles, Scanning Electron Microscopy was performed by Hitachi SU6600 Analytical Variable Pressure FE-SEM (Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope) at Sri Lanka Institute of Nanotechnology (SLINTEC).

Treatments and data collection

Nanoparticle suspensions of different concentrations were prepared by weighing the prepared nano-ZnO particles and were suspended in double deionized water. Nano-ZnO fertilizer was used in spray applications at a concentration of 30 and 60 and 120 mg L⁻¹ (F1, F2 and F3) and double deionized water served as the control (F0).

The treatments were carried out at two stages as foliar spray application. During the bearing stage [at 48-58 Days after sowing (DAS)] and at the stage of grain filling [(100-105 DAS)]. Application was done by using pump sprayers for 30 seconds per plant at a constant rate of spraying.

Growth parameters: plant height and Chlorophyll content were recorded during 30, 60 and 90DAS. Then at the harvest, the yield characters and the percentage grain filling and weight of 100 grains were measured. The number of panicles per plant, number of grains per panicle and length of the panicles were also observed (Plant Genetic Resources Center, Sri Lanka, Characterization of rice Catalogue, 1999).

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics *i.e.*, mean, standard error of mean was calculated and tabulated. Data were subjected to univariate analysis of variance (3-way ANOVA) to assess the interaction between the rice varieties, fertilizer treatment and DAS. The significant level of the results $p \leq 0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant. Non-parametric characters were subjected to χ^2 test. Further, a principle component analysis was carried out for growth-related data to find a component that can describe the variance. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS ver. 20.0.

Results

The highest XRD peak was used in calculating the crystallite size by the Scherrer's equation (Equation 1). The calculated crystallite size of the Nano-ZnO particles was 31 nm (Figure 1).

Figure 1: X-Ray diffraction of ZnO nanoparticles

Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM) analysis of nano-ZnO

FE-SEM (Field Emission SEM) was carried out to observe the surface morphologies of the prepared ZnO nano particles. FE-SEM images of synthesized Nano-ZnO particles are shown in Figure 2. ZnO nanoparticles show agglomeration which results in greater surface area to volume ratio. Particle shape ranged from spherical to hexagonal. The scale is 500nm divided in to 10, therefore the size of the ZnO nanoparticles are in the nano range.

Figure 2: SEM of Synthesized ZnO nano particles

Statistical analysis of yield and growth parameters of rice varieties

According to the results, mean weight of 100 seeds was the highest in ZnO at 60 mgL⁻¹ in treated rice plants. *Kuruluthuda* and *Kalu heenati* showed a prominent increase in seed-weight, compared to *Pacchchaperumal* and *Surwandel* as well as the two reference varieties, Bg360 and Bg94-1 (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Mean weight of 100 seeds of the rice varieties; Bg360, Bg94-1, Kalu heenati, Kurulutuda, Pacchaperumal, and Suwandel

According to the results, mean percentage grain filling was the highest in ZnO at 60 mgL⁻¹ treated rice plants. Traditional rice varieties as well as inbred rice varieties showed percentage grain filling increment when treated with nano-ZnO (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Mean percentage grain filling of the rice varieties, (Bg360, Bg94-1, Bw364, Kalu heenati, Kurulutuda, Pacchaperumal, and Suwandel)

According to the results of growth parameters, mean total chlorophyll content of traditional rice varieties as well as inbred rice varieties showed increased chlorophyll content when treated with nano-ZnO (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Mean of Total Chlorophyll content extracted from the rice varieties; Bg94-1, Pachchaperumal, and Suwandel

Mean chlorophyll content measured with the SPAD meter was increased in traditional rice varieties as well as inbred rice varieties when treated with nano-ZnO.

Figure 6: Mean Chlorophyll content measured by SPAD of rice varieties; Bg360, Kuruluthuda and Kaluheenati

According to the ANOVA performed (Table 1), percentage grain filling and weight of 100 grains were significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) affected by the nano ZnO treatment, in both inbred and traditional rice varieties.

Table 1: Summary of the one way ANOVA performed on percentage grain filling and Weight of 100 seeds

Variety	Character	Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Bg360	weight of 100grains	.590	3	.197	51.498	S*
	%grain filling	.055	3	.018	53.038	S*
Bg94-1	weight of 100grains	6.370	3	2.123	181.618	S*
	%grain filling	.055	3	.018	20.180	S*
<i>Pachchaperumal</i>	weight of 100grains	.414	3	.138	97.818	S*
	%grain filling	316.306	3	135.435	6.699	S*
<i>Suwandel</i>	weight of 100grains	.523	3	.174	58.686	S*
	%grain filling	211.152	3	70.384	4.941	S*
<i>Kalu heenati</i>	weight of 100grains	4.159	3	1.386	28.201	S*
	%grain filling	.017	3	.006	32.742	S*
<i>Kuruluthuda</i>	weight of 100grains	.935	3	.312	49.989	S*
	%grain filling	.033	3	.011	62.788	S*

Table 2 shows that the ANOVA results of plant height and chlorophyll content were not significantly affected by the nano-ZnO treatment in both traditional and inbred rice varieties.

Table 2: Summary of the one –way ANOVA performed on Plant height and Chlorophyll content

Variety	Character	Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Bg360	Height	1791.550	3	597.183	1.014	NS
	Chlorophyll	153.304	3	51.101	1.349	NS
Bg94-1	Height	1576.646	3	525.549	.509	NS
	Chlorophyll	229.980	3	76.660	1.904	NS
<i>Pachchaperumal</i>	Height	1242.036	3	414.012	.473	NS
	Chlorophyll	39.417	3	13.139	2.262	NS
<i>Suwandel</i>	Height	963.469	3	321.156	.423	NS
	Chlorophyll	65.892	3	21.964	.829	NS
<i>Kalu heenati</i>	Height	796.352	3	265.451	.325	NS
	Chlorophyll	81.785	3	27.262	.763	NS

<i>Kuruluthuda</i>	Height	188.686	3	62.895	.051	NS
	Chlorophyll	770.698	3	256.899	.751	NS

Discussion

Results obtained in this study indicated a positive increase of yield-related characteristics on the tested varieties of rice with the use of nano-ZnO. The weights of 100 grain samples of the four rice varieties which was subjected to univariate analysis of variance have notably increased implying of a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) effect created by nano-ZnO concentration on the rice varieties. When the Nano ZnO concentration was increased, the weight of 100 grains also increased and the highest weight was recorded at 60mgL^{-1} . The weight of 100 grain response of the four traditional rice varieties *Kuruluthuda*, *Kaluheenati*, *Pachchaperumal* and *Suwandel* is prominent compared to the inbred varieties Bg360 and Bg94-1. Percentage grain filling is the stage in which the fertilized ovaries develop into mature seeds containing stored food material also known as caryopses. It is an important factor which finally influences grain yield and quality. The results suggest that the percentage grain filing of the four tested rice varieties are significantly affected by the nano-ZnO concentration.

Considering the growth characters, the plant height and chlorophyll content were not significantly affected by nano-ZnO fertilizer treatment. Therefore, it is evident that foliar application of nano-ZnO-fertilizer has a considerable effect on yield/reproductive parameters, but no significant effect on growth parameters in traditional rice varieties when compared with the tested inbred rice varieties. Thus application of nano-ZnO could be considered a feasible and novel method to extend the cultivation and increase the yield of normally low-yielding traditional rice varieties as well as high yielding inbred varieties. Similar results were obtained in studies conducted elsewhere. For instance, in a study conducted by Upadhyaya *et al.* (2015) in India revealed a significantly increased physiological effect with the application of Zinc nano particles on different varieties of rice. Foliar application of the Iranian commercial nano-fertilizer Super micro plus, which contain 8% of Zinc and 0.65% of Copper, has also shown a significant effect on rice growth and yield (Jassim *et al.*, 2019).

The findings of the present study revealed that the foliar application of Zn in the form of a nano fertilizer suspension increases the yield of traditional rice varieties. This could be an alternative method promote cultivation of the traditional rice varieties while reducing the over usage of bulk fertilizers which cause various environmental problems.

Conclusion

The traditional rice varieties *Kalu Heenati*, *Kuruluthuda*, *Suwandel* and *Pachchaperumal* exhibited significantly increased percentage grain filling with the application of nano-ZnO fertilizer. Yield increment in the selected traditional rice varieties was prominent compared to the two inbred varieties Bg360 and Bg94-1 which were used as references. Therefore, nano fertilizers could be used to expand the cultivation of traditional rice varieties which are low yielding under normal conditions, have medicinal properties and are rich in nutrients compared to the inbred rice varieties. The findings would motivate the farmers who are catering to the increasing demand for such varieties of rice in the local markets in Sri Lanka. Further, yield increment that occur due to nano fertilizers is beneficial in terms of food security—because it sustains the nutriments of the soil while yielding higher growth.

Moreover, studies involving the application of nanotechnology in the agriculture sector in Sri Lanka are still at its early stages, and therefore, in-depth studies are required to understand the ideas of optimizing the concentration and the time of application in a variety of modes. Also, such studies could also undertake a close analysis of the repercussions and possible hazardous effects of using Nano fertilizers in the production of rice.

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